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Bureaucratic-Administrative Facilities in the Establishment of Start Ups at a Global Level

Between 2013 and 2019, the administrative bureaucratic procedures for the creation of start-ups were simplified by 16.00% on average for the countries considered

The World Bank calculates the number of procedures necessary to establish a start-up worldwide. Start-up procedures are those necessary to start a business, including interactions to obtain the necessary permits and licenses and to complete all registrations, verifications and notifications to begin operations. The data refers to companies with specific ownership characteristics, size and type of production. The data considered refers to the period between 2013 and 2019. Only countries with a complete historical series in the period analysed were considered.

Ranking of countries by number of procedures necessary to open a start-up in 2019. Venezuela is in first place by number of procedures necessary for a start up with a value of 20 units, followed by Equatorial Guinea with 16, and Bosnia, Eritrea and the Philippines with a value of 13. In mid-table, there are Zambia with 7, and Bahrain, Benin, Cameroon, Chile, Djibouti with a value of 6. Jamaica, Singapore and the Emirates close the ranking United Arab Emirates with a value of 2, Georgia and New Zealand

Ranking of countries by value of the percentage change in procedures necessary to open a start-up between 2013 and 2019. Slovenia is in first place by value of the percentage change in procedures necessary to open a start-up between 2013 and 2019 with a value equal to 50.00%, followed by Burundi, Malaysia and Sweden with +33.00%, and by Portugal with +20.00%. In the middle of the table are the United States, Uruguay, the West Bank and Gaza, Yemen, and Zambia with a value of 0.00%. The Democratic Republic of Congo closes the ranking with a value of -66.67%, followed by the United Arab Emirates with a value of -66.67%, followed by Tunisia with a value of -72.73%, followed by Saudi Arabia with a value of -78.57% and Brunei Darussalam with -83.33%. Overall between 2013 and 2019 the number of procedures necessary for the establishment of start-ups decreased on average for the countries considered from 7.88 to 6.44 or a reduction equal to -1.2 units equal to -16, 00%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is presented a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Three different types of clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Norway, Israel, Tajikistan, Afghanistan, Senegal, Kyrgyz Republic, Latvia, Tonga, Netherlands, Samoa, Greece, Armenia, Lithuania, Mauritius, Russian Federation, Kosovo, Ireland, South Korea, Estonia, St. Lucia, Marshall Islands, Albania, Uruguay, Belgium,

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Denmark, Dominica, France, Iceland, Luxembourg, Mali, Liberia, Poland, Panama, United Kingdom, Cote d'Ivoire, Azerbaijan, Morocco, Uzbekistan, Burundi, Sweden, Finland, Burkina Faso, Australia, Belarus, Singapore, United Arab Emirates, Moldova, Hong Kong, Jamaica, Slovenia, Canada, Serbia, Cyprus, Sierra Leone, Georgia, Togo, New Zealand, Kazakhstan, Portugal, Niger, Oman, Romania, Yemen, Switzerland, United States, Grenada, Hungary, North Macedonia, Papua New Guinea, Maldives, Timor Leste, Sao Tome and Principe, Rwanda, Ukraine, Thailand, Mauritania;

- Cluster 2: Colombia, Slovak Republic, San Marino, Vietnam, Qatar, Chad, Gabon, Japan, Lebanon, Montenegro, Ghana, Nigeria, Palau, Peru, Croatia, Bhutan, Austria, Czechia, Comoros, Seychelles, Cabo Verde, Botswana, Belize, El Salvador, Bangladesh, Germany, Antigua and Barbuda, Guinea Bissau, Chile, Angola, Guatemala, Egypt, Sri Lanka, Costa Rica, Mongolia, Malawi, Malta, Vanuatu, Mexico, Bahamas, Syrian, Nepal, Spain, Barbados, Nicaragua, Italy, Gambia, Zimbabwe, Djibouti, Lao PDR, Solomon Islands, Trinidad and Tobago, Lesotho, Bulgaria, St. Vincent and the Grenadines, Guyana, Micronesia Fed. Sts, Kiribati, St. Kittis and Nevis, Paraguay, Dominican Republic, Jordan, Zambia, Madagascar, Malaysia, Cambodia, Cameroon, Guinea, South Africa, Benin, Turkey, Central African Republic, Namibia, Mozambique, Libya, Iran, Iraq, China, Brunei Darussalam, Congo, Kenya, Bahrain, Suriname, Tunisia;
- Cluster 3: Bolivia, South Sudan, Ethiopia, Uganda, Bosnia, Eritrea, Argentina, Saudi Arabia, Myanmar, Algeria, Indonesia, India, Pakistan, Haiti, Eswatini, Ecuador, Congo Rep., Honduras, Philippines, Equatorial Guinea, Venezuela, Fiji, Brazil, West Bank and Gaza, Sudan, Tanzania, Kuwait.

From the point of view of clustering, it appears that the value of cluster 3 is dominant compared to the value of cluster 2 and compared to the value of cluster 1. It must be considered that the countries that have a lower level of procedures for the creation of start-ups are essentially in the Western world. The countries that have the least capacity to facilitate the creation of start-ups are found in Latin America and Africa.

Conclusions. Streamlining the procedures for establishing start-ups is an essential element to allow the strengthening of productive and entrepreneurial activities at country level. It is clear that the ability of countries to stimulate entrepreneurship is a necessary element to generate economic growth. The countries that have simplified the procedures for establishing start-ups are also the countries that have greater per capita income and are more dynamic from a capitalistic point of view, technological innovation and the well-being of the population. The countries that have the greatest capacity to promote entrepreneurship are Canada, China, Jamaica, Singapore, United Arab Emirates, Georgia and New Zealand. Currently, the countries that offer greater access to entrepreneurship are the Anglo-Saxon countries, some Middle Eastern countries and some Asian countries. Although Europe still has entrepreneurship facilitation systems, it is unable to be competitive with areas characterized by start-up dynamism. It is therefore necessary to intervene above all at a European level to facilitate the establishment of start-ups considering that they not only play an important function in the creation of technological innovation but also allow access to social mobility by generating the so-called "*nouveau riche*". Compared to Anglo-Saxon, Middle Eastern and Asian countries, Europe appears backward. Moreover, to recover competitiveness it should allow a streamlining of the bureaucratic procedures necessary for the establishment of start-ups.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Rank	Country Name	2019	Rank	Country Name	2019	Rank	Country Name	2019	Rank	Country Name	2019
1	Venezuela, RB	20	48	Chad	8	95	Cameroon	6	142	Belarus	4
2	Equatorial Guinea	16	49	Ghana	8	96	Chile	6	143	Burundi	4
3	Bosnia and Herzegovina	13	50	Japan	8	97	Djibouti	6	144	Congo, Dem. Rep.	4
4	Eritrea	13	51	Lebanon	8	98	Gambia, The	6	145	Cote d'Ivoire	4
5	Philippines	13	52	Malaysia	8	99	Grenada	6	146	Kazakhstan	4
6	Uganda	13	53	Mexico	8	100	Guatemala	6	147	Kyrgyz Republic	4
7	Algeria	12	54	Mongolia	8	101	Guinea	6	148	Latvia	4
8	Argentina	12	55	Montenegro	8	102	Hungary	6	149	Lithuania	4
9	Bolivia	12	56	Nepal	8	103	Lesotho	6	150	Mauritania	4
10	Eswatini	12	57	Palau	8	104	Maldives	6	151	Mauritius	4
11	Haiti	12	58	Peru	8	105	Myanmar	6	152	Morocco	4
12	South Sudan	12	59	Qatar	8	106	North Macedonia	6	153	Netherlands	4
13	Brazil	11	60	Suriname	8	107	Papua New Guinea	6	154	Niger	4
14	Congo, Rep.	11	61	Syrian Arab Republic	8	108	Portugal	6	155	Norway	4
15	Ecuador	11	62	Vietnam	8	109	Puerto Rico	6	156	Oman	4
16	Ethiopia	11	63	Bahamas, The	7	110	Romania	6	157	Russian Federation	4
17	Fiji	11	64	Barbados	7	111	Sao Tome and Principe	6	158	Samoa	4
18	Honduras	11	65	Bulgaria	7	112	Switzerland	6	159	Senegal	4
19	Indonesia	11	66	Colombia	7	113	Timor-Leste	6	160	Sweden	4
20	West Bank and Gaza	11	67	Croatia	7	114	Ukraine	6	161	Tonga	4
21	Central African Republic	10	68	Dominican Republic	7	115	United States	6	162	United Kingdom	4
22	Costa Rica	10	69	Gabon	7	116	Yemen, Rep.	6	163	Armenia	3
23	India	10	70	Guyana	7	117	Albania	5	164	Australia	3
24	Iran, Islamic Rep.	10	71	Italy	7	118	Belgium	5	165	Azerbaijan	3
25	Libya	10	72	Jordan	7	119	China	5	166	Brunei Darussalam	3
26	Mozambique	10	73	Kenya	7	120	Cyprus	5	167	Burkina Faso	3

27	Namibia	10	74	Kiribati	7	12 1	Denmark	5	16 8	Estonia	3
28	Sudan	10	75	Malawi	7	12 2	Dominica	5	16 9	Finland	3
29	Tanzania	10	76	Micronesia, Fed. Sts.	7	12 3	Egypt, Arab Rep.	5	17 0	Greece	3
30	Antigua and Barbuda	9	77	Nicaragua	7	12 4	France	5	17 1	Ireland	3
31	Bangladesh	9	78	Nigeria	7	12 5	Iceland	5	17 2	Israel	3
32	Belize	9	79	Paraguay	7	12 6	Kuwait	5	17 3	Korea, Rep.	3
33	Botswana	9	80	San Marino	7	12 7	Liberia	5	17 4	Kosovo	3
34	Cabo Verde	9	81	Serbia	7	12 8	Luxembourg	5	17 5	Moldova	3
35	Cambodia	9	82	Slovak Republic	7	12 9	Madagascar	5	17 6	Saudi Arabia	3
36	Comoros	9	83	Solomon Islands	7	13 0	Mali	5	17 7	Slovenia	3
37	Czechia	9	84	South Africa	7	13 1	Malta	5	17 8	Tajikistan	3
38	El Salvador	9	85	Spain	7	13 2	Marshall Islands	5	17 9	Togo	3
39	Germany	9	86	Sri Lanka	7	13 3	Pakistan	5	18 0	Tunisia	3
40	Guinea-Bissau	9	87	St. Kitts and Nevis	7	13 4	Panama	5	18 1	Uzbekistan	3
41	Iraq	9	88	St. Vincent and the Grenadines	7	13 5	Poland	5	18 2	Canada	2
42	Lao PDR	9	89	Trinidad and Tobago	7	13 6	Rwanda	5	18 3	Hong Kong SAR, China	2
43	Seychelles	9	90	Turkiye	7	13 7	Sierra Leone	5	18 4	Jamaica	2
44	Zimbabwe	9	91	Vanuatu	7	13 8	St. Lucia	5	18 5	Singapore	2
45	Angola	8	92	Zambia	7	13 9	Thailand	5	18 6	United Arab Emirates	2
46	Austria	8	93	Bahrain	6	14 0	Uruguay	5	18 7	Georgia	1
47	Bhutan	8	94	Benin	6	14 1	Afghanistan	4	18 8	New Zealand	1

Country Name	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Afghanistan	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Albania	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Algeria	13	13	12	12	12	12	12
Angola	8	8	8	7	8	8	8
Antigua and Barbuda	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Argentina	14	14	14	14	14	11	12
Armenia	4	4	4	4	4	3	3
Australia	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Austria	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Azerbaijan	3	4	3	3	3	3	3
Bahamas, The	7	7	8	8	7	7	7
Bahrain	7	7	7	6	6	6	6
Bangladesh	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Barbados	8	7	7	7	7	7	7
Belarus	6	6	5	5	5	4	4
Belgium	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Belize	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Benin	8	8	8	6	6	6	6

Bhutan	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Bolivia	14	14	14	14	12	12	12
Bosnia and Herzegovina	13	13	13	13	13	13	13
Botswana	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Brazil	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
Brunei Darussalam	18	18	7	7	5	3	3
Bulgaria	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Burkina Faso	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Burundi	3	3	3	3	3	4	4
Cabo Verde	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Cambodia	12	12	8	9	9	9	9
Cameroon	7	7	7	7	7	6	6
Canada	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Central African Republic	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Chad	9	9	9	9	9	8	8
Chile	8	8	8	8	8	7	6
China	13	11	11	9	9	5	5
Colombia	9	9	9	8	8	8	7
Comoros	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Congo, Dem. Rep.	12	8	7	7	4	4	4
Congo, Rep.	12	12	12	12	11	11	11
Costa Rica	9	9	9	9	9	10	10
Cote d'Ivoire	6	5	5	5	5	4	4
Croatia	8	8	8	8	8	8	7
Cyprus	6	6	6	5	5	5	5
Czechia	8	8	8	8	8	9	9
Denmark	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Djibouti	9	7	7	7	7	6	6
Dominica	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Dominican Republic	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Ecuador	13	13	12	11	11	11	11
Egypt, Arab Rep.	9	9	9	9	9	6	5
El Salvador	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Equatorial Guinea	18	18	18	17	16	16	16
Eritrea	13	13	13	13	13	13	13
Estonia	5	4	3	3	3	3	3
Eswatini	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Ethiopia	14	14	14	14	12	11	11
Fiji	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
Finland	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
France	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Gabon	9	9	9	9	8	7	7
Gambia, The	8	7	7	7	7	7	6
Georgia	2	2	2	2	2	1	1
Germany	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Ghana	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Greece	5	5	5	5	4	4	3

Grenada	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Guatemala	9	9	9	9	9	6	6
Guinea	7	7	7	7	7	6	6
Guinea-Bissau	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Guyana	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Haiti	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Honduras	13	13	11	11	11	11	11
Hong Kong SAR, China	3	3	2	2	2	2	2
Hungary	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Iceland	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
India	14	15	14	14	12	10	10
Indonesia	12	13	13	12	12	11	11
Iran, Islamic Rep.	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Iraq	11	11	10	10	9	9	9
Ireland	4	4	4	3	3	3	3
Israel	5	5	5	4	4	4	3
Italy	8	7	7	7	7	7	7
Jamaica	5	2	2	2	2	2	2
Japan	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Jordan	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Kazakhstan	7	7	6	5	5	5	4
Kenya	13	13	13	9	7	7	7
Kiribati	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Korea, Rep.	4	4	4	3	3	3	3
Kosovo	5	4	4	3	3	3	3
Kuwait	12	12	12	12	9	7	5
Kyrgyz Republic	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Lao PDR	9	9	10	10	10	10	9
Latvia	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Lebanon	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Lesotho	7	7	7	7	7	7	6
Liberia	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Libya	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Lithuania	6	5	4	4	4	4	4
Luxembourg	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Madagascar	9	9	10	8	5	5	5
Malawi	10	8	8	7	7	7	7
Malaysia	6	6	6	9	9	9	8
Maldives	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Mali	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Malta	10	10	10	9	8	8	5
Marshall Islands	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Mauritania	9	7	7	7	4	4	4
Mauritius	5	5	5	5	5	4	4
Mexico	7	7	7	8	8	8	8
Micronesia, Fed. Sts.	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Moldova	7	6	5	5	4	3	3

Mongolia	7	7	8	8	8	8	8
Montenegro	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Morocco	6	6	5	5	4	4	4
Mozambique	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Myanmar	15	15	14	12	12	12	6
Namibia	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Nepal	7	7	7	7	8	8	8
Netherlands	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
New Zealand	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Nicaragua	8	7	7	7	7	7	7
Niger	7	7	7	5	4	4	4
Nigeria	8	8	8	8	8	8	7
North Macedonia	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Norway	5	4	4	4	4	4	4
Oman	7	7	7	5	4	4	4
Pakistan	13	13	13	13	13	10	5
Palau	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Panama	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Papua New Guinea	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Paraguay	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Peru	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Philippines	17	17	17	17	17	14	13
Poland	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Portugal	5	6	6	6	6	6	6
Puerto Rico	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Qatar	9	9	9	9	9	8	8
Romania	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Russian Federation	6	5	5	4	4	4	4
Rwanda	7	8	7	5	5	5	5
Samoa	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
San Marino	9	8	8	8	8	8	7
Sao Tome and Principe	7	6	6	6	6	6	6
Saudi Arabia	14	14	14	14	11	11	3
Senegal	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Serbia	6	6	6	5	5	5	7
Seychelles	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Sierra Leone	6	6	6	5	5	5	5
Singapore	3	3	3	3	3	2	2
Slovak Republic	9	9	8	8	8	8	7
Slovenia	2	2	2	2	2	3	3
Solomon Islands	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
South Africa	6	7	7	7	7	7	7
South Sudan	13	13	13	13	12	12	12
Spain	11	7	7	7	7	7	7
Sri Lanka	9	9	8	7	7	7	7
St. Kitts and Nevis	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
St. Lucia	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

St. Vincent and the Grenadines	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Sudan	11	11	11	11	11	10	10
Suriname	13	13	13	8	8	8	8
Sweden	3	3	3	3	3	4	4
Switzerland	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Syrian Arab Republic	7	7	7	7	8	8	8
Tajikistan	5	4	4	5	4	4	3
Tanzania	11	11	11	11	11	10	10
Thailand	7	7	7	6	5	5	5
Timor-Leste	8	6	5	5	6	6	6
Togo	7	6	6	5	5	4	3
Tonga	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Trinidad and Tobago	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Tunisia	11	11	11	11	11	7	3
Turkiye	10	11	11	10	10	7	7
Uganda	14	14	14	13	13	13	13
Ukraine	7	7	5	6	6	6	6
United Arab Emirates	6	6	6	4	4	2	2
United Kingdom	6	6	4	4	4	4	4
United States	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Uruguay	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Uzbekistan	6	6	4	4	3	3	3
Vanuatu	8	8	8	7	7	7	7
Venezuela, RB	19	20	20	20	20	20	20
Vietnam	9	9	9	9	9	8	8
West Bank and Gaza	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
Yemen, Rep.	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Zambia	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Zimbabwe	10	10	10	10	9	9	9

